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Research Article

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DEMOGRAPHIC AND RADIOGRAPHIC FEATURES OF THE SCHNEIDERIAN MEMBRANE AND PERIAPICAL AND PERIODONTAL DISORDERS BY MEANS OF CONE BEAM COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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Abstract:

Aim: This examination embraced to survey the neurotic and spatial relationship among periapical and periodontal infections of the maxillary first molars and thickening of maxillary sinus mucosa with cone-shaft registered tomography.

Methods: An aggregate of 138 CBCT pictures of subjects 23–65 years old assessed reflectively. The patients' sex and age and segment and pathologic discoveries of the maxillary sinus in the main molar territory were recorded, reviewed and analyzed. Our current research was conducted at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020.

Results. Approximately 58% of the patients were male and 43% female, with little contrast in the thickness of the Schneiderian film between men and women. Based on the rating of the periapical record, the highest recurrence was detected in collection 1. Considering the side effects of ANOVA, there were no critical contrasts in the frequencies of endodontic periodontal lesions and an expansion of the schneiderian film thickness. There were critical connections between the periapical and periodontal contaminations ($P < 0.002$) and the thickness of the schneiderian layer. In addition, a critical connection transport was identified between the thickness of the Schneiderian film and the distance between the sinus floor and the root apophyses ($P = 0.39$).

Conclusion: A review of the CBCT imaging revealed that periapical lesions and periodontal contamination in the back territory of the maxilla were related to the thickening of the Schneiderian layer. In addition, there was a significant relationship between the area of the maxillary back teeth, such as the thickness of the bone from the root peak to the floor of the maxillary sinus, and the thickness of the Schneiderian layer.

Keywords: Demographic, Radiographic Features, Schneiderian Membrane, Periapical And Periodontal Disorders.

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INTRODUCTION:

It is very important to replace teeth lost during dental care to restore mastication, speech and smile. This is done using fixed and removable prosthetic machines and root structure inserts. Currently, the use of root implants is the best treatment method for replacing lost teeth, in which the implant is placed inside the jaw bones and ensures the necessary reliability through the integration of osteo synthesis somewhere in the range of bones and implants [1]. Currently, one of the difficulties in dentistry is to place inserts into the back jaw bone in cases where the thickness and stature of the bone is inadequate. X-rays show an extraordinary commitment to the early treatment of maxillary sinus lift by showing the presence of hard septa inside the sinus [2], thickening of the Schneiderian layer, annihilation due to a previous sinus lift technique and the presence of pathological elements inside the maxillary sinus, such as intense rhino sinusitis or neoplastic processes [3]. Based on past examinations, 13-15% of cases of maxillary sinusitis should be odontogenic contaminations due to the proximity of the underlying foundations of the maxillary back teeth with the maxillary sinus in the maxilla [4]. An investigation showed that 99% of the 139 cases of maxillary sinusitis were associated with teeth that caused changes in the integrity of the sinus floor. It is believed that apical periodontitis, periodontal diseases, the treatment of the embedding and the extraction of the teeth rise the risks of maxillary sinusitis. Asymptomatic persons may present a slight expansion of the thickness of the maxillary sinus layer, which is considered normal; however, if the thickness is > 5 mm on MRI evaluation, this is considered as an indication of sinusitis and conceivable pathological elements in the sinus. It is difficult to envisage significant anatomical regions of the maxillary sinus adjacent to the foundations of the molars due to the superposition of contiguous structures. CT filter evaluations are generally used for the evaluation of the paranasal sinuses. CBCT is a new 3D imaging modality that has been used for maxillofacial evaluations of teeth since 1998. It requires less exposure to radiation and gives an image quality equivalent to that of the CT technique. Currently, this method is used by dental specialists and otolaryngologists for the evaluation of paranasal sinuses. The objective of the current study is to use the CBCT method to evaluate the segment and radio-

realistic qualities of the Schneiderian layer and their relationship with periodontal and periapical infections [5].

METHODOLOGY:

Prohibition measures consisted of CBCT images of subjects with complete maxillary edentulous, patients with maxillary insertions, patients with a background of intense maxillary sinus injury, patients with suspicious protrusions in the maxillary back, and patients with a background of bony unions in the maxillary back. The pattern of incorporation was that of patients with maxillary first molars. Our current research was conducted at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. A total of 137 CBCT images from subjects aged 23 to 66 years were evaluated, including 79 males and 64 females. In cases where the distinction between the eye-controls was greater than 0.4 mm, the images were re-evaluated and the mean of the spectator-detailed qualities was taken into account and used. To begin with, the radiographs were evaluated according to endodontic and periodontal problems of the teeth and divided into 5 groups according to the periapical list scoring, the periapical condition was evaluated as follows : 1) typical periapical structures; 2) minor changes in bone structure; 3) some changes in bone structure with some mineral deficiency; 4) periodontitis with a highly characterized radiolucent area; and 5) extreme periodontitis with intensification features. The sexual orientations of the patients were also recorded. At the next stage, the teeth were evaluated for the presence of periapical and periodontal lesions, then the distance between the floor of the maxillary sinus and the apex closest to the base of the main molar (figure 1, A) and the alveolar peak closest to the main molar on the buccal or lingual perspective (figure 1, B) was verified. The more it is hidden, the more the thickness of the buccopalatal in the area above the main molar peak was resolved in the coronal measurement (Figure 2). In the next step, a line was drawn in front of the line associating the palatal peaks of the main molars on both sides to measure the depth of the sense of taste (Figure 3). Finally, the thickness of the Schneiderian film was resolved at three locations in the maxilla: medium, parallel and mediocre. The average of the three qualities was then used as a perspective source (figure 4).

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

Figure 4:

RESULTS:

Of the 136 examples in the current survey, 87 (61 per cent) were in the first group (men) and 57 (42 per cent) were in the second group (women). The T-test was used to study the stand-alone examples and their circulations. For endodontic-periodontal lesions, the highest mean recurrence was recorded in group 1

(2.89 ± 2.92) and the lowest in group 5 (6.72 ± 5.07) (Table 1). No critical contrast was found in the thickness of the Schneiderian layer in male and female subjects. The ANOVA did not show measurable contrasts between the frequencies of endodontic-periodontal lesions and an expansion of the Schneiderian layer thickness. In addition, intra-group

evaluations with the Tukey test did not show significant contrasts between different groupings with endodontic-periodontal lesions. Pearson's connection coefficient showed significant connections between periapical and periodontal contaminations ($P<0.001$), sense of taste depth ($P=0.021$) and Schneiderian layer thickness. There were no critical connections between periapical and different factors. In addition, there were huge connecting vessels between periodontal

contaminations and the depth of the sense of taste ($P<0.001$), the distance between the sinus floor and the root apexes ($P=0.04$), and the thickness of the Schneiderian film ($P=0.37$). In addition, there were critical relationships between peak height and depth of taste sense ($P=0.018$), the correct paths between the sinus floor and root tips ($P<0.001$), and the thickness of the Schneiderian layer ($P=0.044$).

Table 1:

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Upper Bound	Maximum
1	100	2.8762	2.91084	.29108	2.2986	3.4538	.64	16.82
2	7	3.8700	3.75068	1.41762	.4012	7.3388	1.29	12.09
3	15	3.1013	2.85271	.73657	1.5216	4.6811	.66	11.04
4	7	6.3243	5.91564	2.23590	.8532	11.7953	2.26	18.59
5	3	5.7067	4.05450	2.34086	-4.3653	15.7786	1.28	9.24
Total	132	3.2017	3.24680	.28260	2.6426	3.7607	.64	18.59

ificant differences between the different groups with

ificant relationship between the thickness of the

Table 2:

		p.a.inf	perio.inf	pal. depth	BP. width	os. height. apex	os. height. crest	schneiderian
p.a.inf	Pearson Correlation	1	.369**	-.0181*	.100	.120	.072	.356**
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000	.019	.126	.085	.206	.000
	N	132	132	132	132	132	132	132
perio.inf	Pearson Correlation	.369**	1	-.303**	-.019	.164*	.045	.156*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000		.000	.416	.030	.306	.037
	N	132	132	132	132	132	132	132
pal. depth	Pearson Correlation	-.181*	-.303**	1	.061	.094	.187*	-.074
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.019	.000		.242	.142	.016	.198
	N	132	132	132	132	132	132	132
BP. width	Pearson Correlation	.100	-.019	.061	1	.139	.095	-.111
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.126	.416	.242		.056	.138	.103
	N	132	132	132	132	132	132	132
os. height. apex	Pearson Correlation	.120	.164*	.094	.139	1	.728**	-.155*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.085	.030	.142	.056		.000	.038
	N	132	132	132	132	132	132	132
os. height. crest	Pearson Correlation	.072	.045	.187*	.095	.728**	1	-.151*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.206	.306	.016	.138	.000		.042
	N	132	132	132	132	132	132	132
schneiderian	Pearson Correlation	.356**	.156*	-.074	-.111	-.155*	-.151*	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.037	.198	.103	.038	.042	
	N	132	132	132	132	132	132	132

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

DISCUSSION:

Accurate data on the vital structures of the maxillary sinuses and their anatomical varieties is essential for

safe medical interventions in the maxillary back area [6]. Appropriate information on the vital structures of the area includes the results of a precise medical

procedure and prevents complications [7]. Several studies have studied septa of the maxillary sinus, concluding that these septa are more normal in edentulous patients with an atrophic maxilla than in those with a dentate maxilla, the septa of the edentulous atrophic maxilla being generally more limited than those of the dentate maxilla [8]. In addition, the prevalence rate of septa was not adapted to persistent age and gender. Many creators have considered the presence of septa if the stature is assessed to be >3.6 mm [9]. In a review by Lee *et al*, the septa zone was explored, and a higher prevalence rate was found in the central district (distal part of the second premolar to distal part of the next molar) (half), followed by the most anterior (mesial to distal part of the next premolar) (25.1%) and posterior (distal part of the second molar district) (23.8%), hence predictable with the consequences of previous studies [10].

CONCLUSION:

Under the restrictions of the current investigation, there was a relation between the presence of periapical injuries and periodontal diseases in the dorsal region of the maxilla and the thickening of the schneiderian layer. In addition, there was a huge relationship between the area of the maxillary posterior teeth, such as the bone thickness from the root peak to the maxillary sinus floor and, in addition, from the alveolar peak to the maxillary sinus floor, and the thickness of the schneiderian layer.

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